

EFFECT OF GAMMA RADIATION ON ENZYME HOMEOSTASIS

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Abstract: Gamma radiation had no effect on the body weight of rats. The aim was to study enzyme homeostasis when the body of rats is exposed to gamma radiation.

Changes in amylase and pepsinogen enzymes in the blood and salivary glands under the influence of gamma radiation indicate that the salivary glands are important in the homeostasis of enzymes.

Key words: Salivary glands. Amylolytic activity. γ -radiation. Amount of pepsinogen.

Techniques of conducting experiments on animals. The effect of γ -irradiation on enzyme homeostasis was studied in rats. Adult male white rats weighing 150-200 g were used in the experiment. Rats were irradiated using the "Terabalt-80" remote radiotherapy device with a surface distance of 80 cm from the radioisotope source. Irradiation dose is 0.86-0.85 Gr/min. The amount of ingested dose is 4 Gray. Irradiation time is 3-4 minutes and 30 seconds. After 1, 3, 10, 20, 30, 60 days, the irradiated rats were decapitated under anesthesia and the activity of amylase, lipase, pepsinogen enzymes was determined in the blood.

Secretion of pancreatic enzymes into the blood from acinocytes through the basolateral membrane has been morphologically proven. Pancreatic hydrolases are transported into the blood by several mechanisms: from the small intestine cavity, from degraded acinocytes, from the excretory ducts of the gland, and from acinocytes. The proportion of these mechanisms depends on the functional state of the pancreas and small intestine, the permeability of their histogematic barrier, the amount of pressure in the excretory tract, and the level of their blood supply.

Decrease of amylolytic activity in blood depends on several factors. First, radiation suppresses enzyme synthesis in the pancreas, a certain degree of disturbance in the hemodynamics of the irradiated organ is observed, the structure of the capillary epithelium is disturbed as a result of the permeability change of the histogematic barrier determines the concentration of this enzyme in the blood.

The correlation coefficient of amylase secretion in the parotid gland with the amylolytic activity of the blood is much higher than this indicator of the sublingual and submandibular glands.

From our results, we can conclude that the decrease in the activity of the amylase enzyme in the salivary glands is the result of gamma radiation weakening the secretion of this enzyme in the salivary glands.

Analysis of the obtained results. According to the obtained results, the amylolytic activity of the blood of the experimental rats decreased from the first day after irradiation, especially the amylolytic activity in the blood (α amylase) was sharply reduced by almost two times and had almost the same value until the 20th day, that is, it was 60% compared to the control, on the 30th day of the experiment 90% and 60 days of the experiment remained reliably low compared to the control group.

We know that there are two types of amylase in human blood, pancreatic (p) and salivary (s)

Lipolytic activity in the blood of rats increased under the influence of γ -irradiation on the 1st day of the experiment compared to the control, 3; On the 10th and 20th days, it was found that their activity decreased by a reliable 20%, 25% and 25%, respectively.

The amount of pepsinogen in the blood of rats reliably decreased on the 10th, 20th, and 30th days of γ -irradiation, and on the 60th day of the experiment, this indicator reached the level of the control group.

The analysis of the obtained results gives the opportunity to draw the following conclusions:

1. Amylolytic activity in blood (α amylase) decreased from the first day after irradiation and returned to the initial state at the end of the experiment.
2. Lipolytic activity in the blood of rats decreases on the 3rd day of the experiment and returns to its original level on the 30th day.
3. Irradiation decreases the amount of pepsinogen in salivary gland homogenate and blood of rats on the 10th, 20th and 30th days of the experiment.

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